

Scan me!

Effective Methods of Developing Writing Skills through Reading

¹Nilufar Uktamova [orcid: 0009-0007-4874-9108](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4874-9108)
e-mail: n.yusupova1994@gmail.com

²Mirtolipova Nilufar
e-mail: n.yusupova1994@gmail.com

¹Assistant Teacher, Department of Foreign Philology,

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Tashkent, 100149, Uzbekistan

²The student of second course, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Tashkent, 100149, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: It is possible for the student to acquire basic language skills that will be used throughout his / her life, with the first teaching process of reading and writing planned correctly and effectively. Writing has always been a painful activity for learners. The fact that the duration of the course is limited and that other activities focused more take place in the language teaching puts this skill to the background. The excuse that the students are not well-equipped to do some writing activities can be counted as the reasons given by the related course teachers. Hence, second language learners constantly struggle to achieve language proficiency; therefore, they find it hard to produce written texts. However, reading materials will set a good model for which they can transfer into their own writing. The goal of this study is to put forward writing skills.

Key words: Reading, Model, Structure, Language, Comprehension, Writing Skills

1 Introduction

The aim of today's foreign language teaching is to enable the learner to use the target language correctly and communicate effectively. In other words, the aim is to help the acquisition and development of comprehension and expression skills. In accomplishing this goal, the knowledge areas necessary for learning a foreign language can be developed efficiently through various teaching materials and activities used in the classroom. One of the instructional materials that can be used in this context is the literary genres that are thought to enrich the classroom environment with various features. These genres, which have been widely used in language teaching since the end of the twentieth century, are thought to contribute to the development of basic language skills. As a matter of fact, the fact that there is a close relationship between language and literary genres reveals that these types will contribute to the development of learner's language skills by reflecting various features and vocabulary of foreign language.

2 Methods

The use of literary genres as a teaching technique in the context of foreign language learning and teaching is also very useful for teaching knowledge topics such as vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation in addition to skill development. In addition to the contributions of literary genres, which are loaded with many functions in foreign language teaching, the fact that they reflect the social and functional aspects of language increases the importance of these teaching materials. While these genres present different aspects of language to the learner, they enable the learner to encounter the actual use of the language in different situations and environments, gain linguistic and cultural awareness, and they direct him to use the foreign language correctly.

3 Result

In foreign language teaching, writing skill, which is seen as the last stage of language skills and thought to be the most difficult skill, requires the use of foreign language in writing correctly and in accordance with the rules (Demirel, 2016). This skill can only be improved by practice. It is thought that reading, which is thought to be combined with writing in practice, will improve the writing skill by providing development of thinking. As Öz

(2011) states, “writing skills are directly related to reading skills.” It is aimed that learners in foreign language teaching actively use the information they have gained in the classroom with writing activities and express their thoughts in a foreign language in writing (Güzel & Barın, 2013). These goals can be achieved through various writing activities.

4 Discussion

Demonstrating writing proficiency relies on language proficiency in that language. Without language proficiency students cannot achieve in foreign language learning. Reading is a useful learning tool that can close this gap. Written texts are useful language input sources. Reading, as being one of the four basic skills, is an activity that requires understanding. “Reading is the activity of seeing, perceiving, comprehending and making sense of all words, sentences or writing with all its elements (Durmuş, 2013). In other words, “Reading is the activity of deriving meaning from written symbols through the collaboration of cognitive behaviors and psychomotor skills” (Demirel, 2016). This activity is carried out with the coordination of mind and eye and the meaning of written expressions. Reading is one of the most important sources of information (Fletcher & Portalupi, 2001). One of the important objectives of reading is to enable the foreign learner to understand and interpret the written text in the target language correctly (Güzel & Barın, 2013). Text, meaningful structures consisting of consecutive sentences, words and visuals. All kinds of information, feelings and thoughts are placed in this structure in a logical order (Gargiulo, 2007). According to Elhabiri (2012), the definition of the text is made in different ways according to daily and scientific language. It is a written whole consisting of multiple sentences as it is understood from the word "text" in everyday language. Within the framework of linguistics, not only written words but also oral words are called text.

However, during language acquisition, students regard writing as the most difficult skill. This may be due to the lack of clarity of the objectives and expectations of the teacher concerned or the curriculum prepared. One issue that most foreign language teachers are mistaken about the concept of writing is to expect students to write a complete essay individually without any help. However, when the foreign language teaching process is taken into consideration, it cannot be observed. In fact, the process is the same in teaching mother tongue. Depending on the level of the student, activities such as writing a sentence, a paragraph, a list or note-taking can also be considered as a writing activity in the process followed. (Storch, 2005). Therefore, it is known that activities to gain writing skills have many benefits in language learning and teaching process.

As stated in Akpınar’s (2007) study, writing skills are very important in terms of revealing the weak points of the students and guiding them on this issue. In general, it is possible to state that an effective writing lesson or any writing activity has many consequences for foreign language teachers to deal. In short, writing skills are thought to help achieve the following objectives:

- Reinforcing the structures or words taught,
- Creative thinking of students,
- Determining students’ levels,
- Seeing the learning process more clearly,
- Teaching punctuation marks,
- Improving students’ language skills,
- Better learning of other skills,
- Transforming students’ competence into performance.

5 Acknowledgements

In the classroom environment where foreign language teaching is carried out, reading and writing skills in that language can only develop as long as the practices and exercises that attract the attention of the students are performed. In this context, reading skills can be improved by reading practice, and writing skills can be improved by writing practice. These practices include some activities that should be done before, during and after the main activity. Story as being one of the literary genres written in the target language for the development of reading skills is also very appropriate to use the story and similar resources can be used because it is short and more appropriate for classroom environment.

6 Conclusions

Generally speaking, the aim of today’s foreign language teaching is to enable the learners to acquire high-

level language skills such as creative and critical thinking, communication, using the target language correctly, including skills such as understanding, interpreting and explaining what they read in the target language. In this context, basic language skills are discussed in four groups as reading, writing, speaking and listening. Foreign language teaching is also a combination of these skills in an interactive way. Reading and writing skills are internal activities that do not require mutual communication. It is stated that these two skills are interdependent, complementary and contribute to the development of each other. As Kuta (2008) points out, reading and writing are interdependent processes that improve each other reciprocally. If one process is neglected, the other is damaged. Especially reading activities contribute to the development of writing skills by providing input for writing activities while contributing to the development of reading skills at the same time.

2 Author Contributions

Authors' works were significant in the development of the theoretical framework and provided support in data collection. The article was conducted a thorough review of the final manuscript, played a role in the conceptual development and made valuable additions. All the used works of authors made substantial contributions to the article and have given their approval for the submitted version.

Reference

1. Akpınar, F. (2007). The effect of process-oriented writing instruction on writer's block, writing apprehension, attitudes towards writing instruction and writing performance. Unpublished PhD thesis. Istanbul Technical University, College of Foreign Languages.
2. Demirel, Ö. (2016). Yabancı dil öğretimi, Ankara: Pegem Akademi Yayıncılık.
3. Durmuş, M. (2013). Yabancılar Türkçe öğretimi. Ankara: Grafik Yayınları.
4. Elhabiri, H. (2012-2013). Teaching the Writing Skills through Literary Texts Case of 2nd Year EFL Students at Djilali Liabes University (Doctoral dissertation). Englewood, CO: Libraries Unlimited.
5. Fletcher, R., & Portalupi, J. (2001). Writing workshop. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
6. Gargiulo, T. L. (2007). Once upon a time: Using story-based activities to develop breakthrough communication skills. John Wiley & Sons.
7. Güzel, A. ve Barın, E. (2013). Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğretimi, Ankara: Akçağ
8. Kuta, K. W. (2008). Reading and Writing to Learn. London: Greenwood Publishing.
9. Storch, N. (2005). Collaborative writing: Product, process, and students' reflections. Journal of Second Language Writing, 14(3), 153-173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2005.05.002>
10. Irgasheva, U.R. (2024), The influence of STEAM Technologies to students' professional speech competence in English classes. Modern science and research, 3(1), 458-461. <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27999>
11. O'ktamova N., Toshtanova S. (2023) THE IMPORTANCE OF BODY LANGUAGE IN COMMUNICATION Science and innovation in the education system 2 (7), 85-88.